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COMPLEX OF MACHINES USED IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF STEPPED TERRACES

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Abstract. The article presents a set of machines used in the construction of stepped terraces. Many of these machines and tools are in serial production, and some are produced in experimental batches exclusively at the request of specialized farms.

Keywords: complex, terrace, slope, machine, planner, technology, fruit plantations, laying gardens, soil.

The complex of machines selected for the system should minimize the cost of labor and materials in the production of products, be highly productive, simple in design and at the same time universal, allow aggregation with general-purpose energy facilities with optimal use of their capacities. These general requirements are also imposed on machines used in other branches of the national economy. In addition, the

system of machines as a whole should be complex, corresponding to the natural and geographical conditions of the given agricultural zone [1-5]. A set of machines designed to perform certain strictly alternating operations of agricultural production cannot be permanent. Technological processes carried out by machines are improved over time, technology develops, so the machines included in this system must be constantly updated. The trend in the development of agricultural machinery is aimed at the production of combined machines and units Д 490, Stump puller КП-100, brush cutter Д-174В, stump puller-loader of stones, stumps КПБ-2, stone removal machine УКП-0,6, stone remover УСК-0,7, Ski trailer for stone removal ПТС-1, bulldozers Д- 492 or Д-259А, grader Д-241 М.

It is quite obvious that there is no need to have all the listed cars in one set at the same time. Stone removal machines are used only in areas where there are at least 30 m³ of stones per hectare at the depth of the cultivated soil layer. УКП-0,6 and УСК-0,7 are not suitable for work on slopes, i.e. on slopes with a steepness of more than 10° they are no longer suitable. They do not work well on less steep slopes either. Hence the need to create new stone removal machines that remove both medium and small stones well. Very small stones can be left, because they do not interfere with tillage, contribute to the improvement of water and temperature conditions. When preparing the territory, large and medium-sized stones can be harvested using bulldozers Д-492 or Д-259А in combination with a Д-496 stump-collector and a ЛС-1 ski trailer. Shrubs are cut by the Д-174В machine. To remove stumps, individual trees and large boulders, it is good to use the Д-496 stump puller and the КП-100 stump puller, often these two machines are mutually replaceable. For uprooting very large stones and stumps in the complex, it is necessary to have a К-1А stumping machine of positional action. However, the need for such a machine rarely arises. The complex of works on the preparation of the territory sometimes leads/

Ploughed terracing can be gradual, when terraces are formed over several years, as a result of annual plowing in the transverse direction of the slope of strips of land of a certain width with a rotation of the layer down the slope. It can also be accelerated, when terraces are formed within one year, after multiple passes of the arable implement. In both cases, construction can be carried out using general-purpose plows (trailed and mounted), but with the accelerated method, it is preferable to work with reversible plows, which significantly increase labor productivity. Before the final formation of the terrace profile, if they are intended for perennial plantings, deep loosening of the canvas is required. In the future, the excavation slope of the terrace is formed. The complex of machines used in ploughed terracing includes: general-purpose plows or reversible plows, ripper РТН-2-25 or РН-40, grader Д-241 М. If the farm does not have a grader, instead of it for leveling the canvas ...ПГ1У-50А, ППН 40, ППН-50, grader Д-241 М. It should be noted that during terracing

units that include mounted plantation plows work much better than units with trailed plantation plows. To improve the quality of terracing work, as well as to facilitate the performance of some operations, the mechanization department of the Research Institute of Horticulture and Viticulture named after Academician M.M. Mirzayev has developed a number of devices that deserve attention. In the Bustonlyk district, the most common method of construction of stepped terraces is excavation-fill, which allows you to build stepped terraces on slopes with a steepness of up to 30°, and sometimes up to 35°. But at the same time, this is the most expensive method, because it requires special construction machines. Excavation and bulk terracing has one big drawback. The upper, humus-rich soil layer moves down, where the thickness of the soil cover is small, it is necessary to re-create a humus layer on the terrace canvases, for which the terrace canvas is repeatedly loosened and fertilized.

The technological process of excavation and bulk terracing consists in digging and excavating the earth from the upland side, moving it, filling it on the lower side of the slope and forming the terrace canvas. To perform these operations, a variety of machines are used in different countries, ranging from excavators and bulldozers to simple agricultural implements. However, now we can already talk about a certain complex of machines, which is the minimum and most rational when performing excavation and filling terracing. This complex includes mounted terrasser T-4 or universal bulldozers Д-492 and Д-259А, ripper PHT 2-25 or PH-40, grader Д-241 М. At present, research and design organizations of the country are developing a number of new improved machines and devices that greatly facilitate the performance of excavation and bulk terracing operations.

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